

NAVAI REGION AGRICULTURE

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonning-2030 strategiyasida belgilangan vazifalarni bajarishda qishloq xo'jaligi sohasidagi islohotlar, samaradorlik va muammolariga e'tibor qaratilgan. Jumladan, Navoiy viloyati qishloq xo'jaligining o'ziga xos jihatlari, muammolari va yechimlariga qaratilgan tadqiqotlar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar.

Navoiy, qishloq xo'jaligi, agrar, sug'orish, ekinlar, diversifikatsiya, monokultura, strategiya, tadqiqotlar, izlanishlar, kolxoz, sovxoz, dehqon, fermer, klaster, paxta, g'alla, chorva, samaradorlik.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются реформы, эффективность и проблемы аграрного сектора в рамках реализации задач, обозначенных в Стратегии «Узбекистан-2030». В частности, представлены исследования, посвященные особенностям, проблемам и решениям развития сельского хозяйства Навоийской области.

Ключевые слова

Уточнение, сельское хозяйство, аграрный, орошение, сельскохозяйственные культуры, диверсификация, монокультура, стратегия, исследования, колхоз, совхоз, фермер, кластер, хлопок, зерно, животноводство, эффективность

Abstract

This article examines reforms, efficiency, and challenges in the agricultural sector as part of the implementation of the objectives outlined in the "Uzbekistan 2030" Strategy. Specifically, it presents research on the characteristics, challenges, and solutions for agricultural development in the Navoi region.

Keywords

Clarification, agriculture, agricultural, irrigation, crops, diversification, monoculture, strategy, research, collective farm, state farm, farmer, cluster, cotton, grain, livestock, efficiency

Introduction. "One of our most important tasks in the field of economy," says President Sh. Mirziyoyev, "is to further reform and modernize the

agricultural sector.”[1;155] Indeed, agriculture is one of the oldest and most enduring pillars of the economy.

Presidential Decree No. PF-158 on the Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" sets the goals of realizing the will of our people to build a free, prosperous, powerful New Uzbekistan, creating all opportunities for every citizen to develop their potential, raising a healthy, educated and spiritually mature generation, forming a strong economy that has become an important link in global production, and ensuring justice, the rule of law, security and stability.

In particular, Goal 54 sets out the tasks of developing agriculture, increasing production, and improving the well-being of the population .[2]

Methodology. The methodology of historicism, scientificity, and an interdisciplinary approach was used to cover this topic.

Analysis of literature on the topic . Theoretical and methodological foundations of the issues of increasing the efficiency of socio-economic development and financing of agriculture are studied by foreign scientists L.Sfu, S.Fan, L.Zhzhou in their research on the reforms being carried out on the strategy of agricultural development in the economy based on the experience of China [3;68], INBuzdalov on agricultural development reforms in the Russian state [4;;325], I.Sandu on specific methods of agricultural development based on the integration of science, education and production and its effectiveness [5;73], IGUshachev conducted research on the importance of scientific research in agricultural development and their inclusion in the state program [6;9]. Among local scientists, A. Abdug'aniyev conducted scientific research on agriculture and its role in the economy, its importance and increasing its efficiency [7;340], G. Kh. Kudratov on the role of grain in the agricultural economy in food policy and its cultivation and economic relations in grain farming [8;250], A. M. Ju'rayev on the economic reforms carried out in agriculture in our country [9;766], and R. Husanov, R. Do'stmurodov, Q. A. Choriyev, and N. S. Khushmatov conducted scientific research on the development of agriculture and planning the activities of farmers and farms. [10;49]

Main part. Historically, the history of agriculture in Uzbekistan dates back thousands of years and includes several main historical periods. In particular, in the ancient and medieval periods, the history of irrigated agriculture on the territory of Uzbekistan has very ancient roots. As early as the 3rd millennium BC, complex irrigation structures and canals were built in the Amu Darya and Syrdarya basins, in particular in the Khorezm and Zarafshan oases. Ancient irrigation systems such as the Darg'om Canal attest to the engineering culture of

that era. The population developed a farming culture based on artificial irrigation. In the Middle Ages, crops such as wheat, barley, rice, millet, and cotton were grown. Cotton cultivation was also recorded in Chinese sources about 2,000 years ago.

The conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire in the second half of the 19th century was a turning point in agrarian relations. During the cotton monopoly, the Empire needed raw materials for its textile industry, so much attention was paid to expanding cotton cultivation in Turkestan.

Railroads and ginning plants were built to support cotton exports, and the balance between cotton and food crops began to shift.

During the Soviet era, agricultural policy led to a one-sided development of the economic structure of Uzbekistan. In the early 1930s, complete collectivization of agriculture was carried out, collective farms and state farms were established. The center turned Uzbekistan into the main cotton base of the entire union. A policy of cotton monoculture was pursued, in which a large part of the arable land was allocated exclusively to cotton.

As a result, the diversion of large amounts of Amur and Syrdarya waters to cotton fields has led to serious environmental problems such as the drying up of the Aral Sea, soil salinization, and water resource shortages.

During the years of Uzbekistan's independence, the transition to a market economy began in the agricultural sector. Collective farms and state farms were transformed into "shirkats" (agricultural production cooperatives), and later farms emerged as the main productive force. The cotton monoculture was abandoned and the cultivation of grains, fruits, and vegetables was switched to ensure food security. Currently, a system of agricultural clusters is being introduced, and modern water-saving and digital technologies are being actively implemented. The government is implementing a strategy for the development of agriculture for 2020-2030.[11]

Agriculture in Uzbekistan is an important sector of the country's economy, based on cotton growing, wheat growing, and horticulture. In recent years, thanks to the cluster system, innovations, and state support, there has been a wide diversification (branching) from cotton to fruit and vegetables, livestock farming, and sericulture, which contributes to increasing food security and exports.

The "Strategy for the Development of Agriculture for 2020-2030" was approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019.[12] The main directions of this strategy include the abandonment of state orders in cotton and grain production and the widespread

application of market principles, the active development of a system of vertically integrated clusters covering the entire chain of agricultural products from cultivation to processing and delivery to the consumer, special attention to the introduction of modern technologies, digitalization, “smart” irrigation systems and advanced scientific achievements in agriculture, the modernization of irrigation systems and the expansion of water-saving technologies (drip irrigation) in conditions of water scarcity, the development of fruit and vegetable growing, livestock breeding and other sectors of the economy, and the creation of an added value chain by increasing the processing capacity of agricultural products.

At this point, it is also necessary to dwell on the main problems that are evident in the agricultural sector. A number of problems remain in this area. In particular,

- Depletion of water resources and decline in soil fertility.
- Aging infrastructure, especially problems with electricity supply and irrigation systems.
- These include some of the shortcomings in protecting farmers' land use rights.

In general, the government of Uzbekistan is pursuing an active policy to transform agriculture into a market-oriented, competitive, and export-oriented sector.

The uniqueness of the Navoi region is also reflected in agricultural reforms, as the region's unique climatic conditions, in particular the vastness of the desert and pasture zones, water scarcity, and soil salinity are pressing issues.

In this regard, the Navoi Agricultural Research and Production Center, as well as other research institutions, and leading scientists are conducting research in this area. In particular, research is being conducted in areas such as livestock and pasture use, irrigated agriculture and water-saving technologies, soil fertility and degradation, crop diversification, and new varieties, innovations, and agrarian policy. In this regard, solutions are being found to issues such as the development of camel, horse and goat breeding in areas mainly based on livestock farming, since most of them are located in the Kyzylkum desert, rational use of available water, use of international technologies in livestock care, and effective use of irrigation systems.

In fact, agriculture in Navoi region is one of the important sectors of the regional economy, characterized mainly by cotton growing, grain growing,

livestock breeding, and, more recently, reforms aimed at introducing water-saving technologies.

In recent years, reforms in this area have achieved a number of indicators. In the first quarter of 2025, an increase of 104.4% was observed compared to the same period last year. In 2024, 86.5 thousand tons of cotton and 258.1 thousand tons of grain were harvested. Repeated planting of crops on land areas freed from grain is being actively carried out. The dynamics of growth in the number of livestock and poultry has been observed.[13]

Conclusion: To address the problem of water scarcity due to natural climatic conditions, much attention has been paid to the introduction of water-saving technologies. In particular, 724 km of irrigation networks have been concreted, and management of 10 pumping stations has been transferred to the private sector.

In agriculture, highly efficient, water and resource-saving methods, such as cotton cultivation based on Chinese-Xinjiang technology, have been introduced. The agricultural sector is one of the main factors in ensuring employment of the population, especially the rural population. The Faculty of Agriculture has been established at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology.

In general, agriculture in Navoi region is developing alongside industry, striving to increase efficiency through rational use of existing water resources, updating technologies, and diversification.

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